

Making Advertising Video as Promotional Media using the Capcut Application at Instagram Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to create advertising videos as a promotional medium by utilizing the CapCut application to enhance the visual appeal and quality of Dinikoe Keramik's promotional content. This research used the action research method with calculations using Epic Rate. Data collection techniques were carried out through the distribution of questionnaires. The video production process was carried out by designing the content concept, recording the ceramic production process, and editing the video using the CapCut application. The results of this study indicated that the use of CapCut as a video editing tool enhanced the visual quality and appeal of promotional content. This was demonstrated by the results of a questionnaire distributed to 16 individuals, including 1 company owner, 1 company employee, 2 design experts, 2 marketing experts, and 10 potential consumers. The findings conclude that the use of the CapCut app in creating advertising videos has proven to be an effective, attractive, and affordable promotional medium for micro businesses such as Dinikoe Keramik. This innovation is expected to support the improvement of digital marketing strategies and reach a wider audience through social media.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Technological developments are currently growing very rapidly and bringing significant changes in various aspects of human life. Technology exists to make human work easier, and one example is the ease of obtaining information through videos. Video is often used as a promotional medium and can be found widely on online platforms in the form of advertisements. According to Kotler and Keller (2019), advertising is a marketing approach that involves creating, selecting, sharing, and amplifying engaging, relevant, and useful content for a clear target audience. Therefore, advertising distribution is very important so that messages can reach and be accepted by the wider community. One effective platform for advertising dissemination is Instagram.

Instagram is a popular social media platform in Indonesia and is considered very effective for spreading information such as advertisements. Atmoko and Bambang Dwi (2012:28) describe Instagram as an application for sharing photos and videos that allows users to capture, edit, and share them across various social networks. Based on available data, Instagram ranks as the most widely used social media platform by Indonesians. This makes Instagram a strategic medium for businesses to carry out digital promotions.

Dinikoe Ceramics, a micro business in Malang City engaged in ceramic crafts, has realized the importance of keeping up with technological developments to expand its marketing reach. However, its promotional activities on Instagram have not been maximized, as shown by the average engagement of posts that remain below 200 views. The 40 videos uploaded previously were less attractive because they only focused on the production process without additional editing elements to capture audience interest. Therefore, the use of CapCut, an accessible and user-friendly video editing application, is expected to improve the quality of Dinikoe Ceramics' advertising videos. CapCut's features allow the creation of attractive, professional, and affordable video content. Based on these considerations, this study is entitled "Making Advertising Video as Promotional Media Using the CapCut Application at Instagram Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City."

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

According to Kotler and Keller (2016), marketing is identifying and meeting human and social needs. One of the good and concise definitions of marketing is to meet needs in a profitable way. Another opinion by According to Tjiptono and Diana (2020:3), marketing is the process of creating, distributing, promoting, and pricing goods, services, and ideas to facilitate satisfactory exchange relationships with customers and to build and maintain positive relationships with stakeholders in a dynamic environment. According to Tjiptono (2016:63), overall marketing management is a way for companies to do business that prepare, determine, and distribute products, services, and ideas that can meet the needs of the target market.

Marketing Mix

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2016), Marketing Mix is a series of tactical marketing tools that can control products, place prices (distribution), promotions that are combined by companies to generate the desired response of the company in the target market. Another opinion by According to Limakrisna and Julius (2016), the marketing mix is a component of the elements that make up your mix strategy, which you want to design with the intention of generating the response you want from your target market. The concept of marketing mix according to Kotler and Keller (2016) consists of 4P, namely product, price, place, and promotion.

Promotions

According to Kotler, Philip and Armstrong (2014) explains that promotional activities are activities that function to convince customers by showing the product or service so that it can persuade customers to buy it. Another opinion by Lupiyoadi (2013) explained further about the definition of promotion, the activity of promotion is what the company does to communicate the benefits of the product and as a tool to influence consumers in purchasing or using services according to needs. Based on the understanding of the experts above, it can be concluded that promotion is a communication activity carried out by a person or company to the wider community to offer a product or service to attract customers to use the product or service.

Promotional Mix

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2014) promotional mix is a special combination of advertising, private sales, sales promotion and public relations. Another opinion by Dharmnumesta (2014) that the definition of the promotion mix is the main elements of communication controlled by the market, including advertising, sales promotion, public relations, face-to-face sales and direct marketing. While the promotion mix according to Kotler and Keller (2016), the promotion mix is the best combination of promotional elements used to achieve the company's goals. The promotional mix has 5 elements as follows: 1) Advertising, 2) Sales Promotion, 3) Direct Marketing, 4) Personal Selling, 5) Public Relation.

Video

According to Khosiyono, et al. (2022:4) "Video is the recording and reproduction of moving visual images". Videos can combine sequences of images to form moving images. Meanwhile, according to Sadiman in Dianawati (2022:40) "Video is an audio-visual media that displays images and sounds". The message presented can be in the form of facts (events, important events, news) or fictitious (e.g. stories), informative, educational or instructional. According to Melinda (2020), learning video media is an audio and visual media that can display an object that moves simultaneously accompanied by natural or appropriate sounds. Helps improve students' understanding of learning. Based on the definitions of the three experts, it can be concluded that video is a medium of recording and reproduction of audio visuals that display sound or moving images presented in the form of facts or fictitious that are informative, educational and instructional.

Instagram

According to Atmoko, Bambang Dwi (2012:28) "Instagram is an application for sharing photos and videos that allows users to take photos, as well as videos, apply digital filters and share them to various social networking services, including Instagram itself". Instagram is a social media that is suitable to be used as a promotional medium with various features.

Capcut

According to Hairum Fellayati (2022), Capcut is a Video Editing app developed by Bytedance Pte. Ltd is android based which is easy to use and can be downloaded for free. Capcut is currently an application that is quite popular with the Indonesian people, especially for fans TikTok. CapCut can be said to have complete features. Starting from animations, stickers, effects, backgrounds, and so on, you can use them at will. Even access can be done offline.

Conceptual Research

Figure 1. Conceptual Research

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Dinikoe Ceramics currently uses Instagram to promote its products through videos and photos, but the existing videos are less engaging because they lack storylines, clear themes, and creative techniques. To improve this, new advertising videos will be produced by combining product, price, location, promo, and selling unit information, then edited with text, audio, and transitions using CapCut to make them more attractive. The effectiveness of these videos will be measured using the EPIC Model to see if they support promotional activities before being published on Instagram.

III. METHOD

The scope of this study is the creation of videos that are used as advertising media using applications CapCut. The content of this advertising video includes company information, production location, product price and quality as well as product details. This research uses the Action Research research procedure. Based on the theory of the action research cycle proposed by Kemmis & Mc Taggart in Arikunto (2020:137-140) it is divided into four cycles, namely planning, implementation of actions, observation, and reflection.

Before entering these cycles, the researcher first diagnosed the problems faced by the company. Initial data collection was conducted through interviews with the Founder of Dinikoe Ceramics to obtain direct insights about the use of social media as a promotional medium and to confirm the feasibility of this research. The findings provided background information that allowed the researcher to begin the study. The unit of analysis involved 16 respondents, including the company owner, one employee, two marketing experts, two design experts, and ten potential consumers. This collaboration aimed to assess and validate the effectiveness of the promotional video created.

Data were collected through observation, interviews, questionnaires, documentation, and literature studies. These methods ensured comprehensive information was obtained to support the research objectives and evaluate the effectiveness of the advertising videos. The questionnaire was developed based on the four dimensions of the EPIC Model (Durianto, 2003), namely Empathy, Persuasion, Impact, and Communication. Each dimension was translated into several indicators, such as attractiveness of design, clarity of information, credibility, ability to generate buying interest, and ease of message understanding.

These indicators were then converted into questionnaire items to be assessed by respondents using a Likert scale. The collected data were then analyzed through several steps, including measuring responses with the Likert scale, conducting simple tabulation analysis, calculating average scores, and finally applying the EPIC Rate formula to determine the overall effectiveness of the advertising video.

IV. RESULTS

First Observation

The initial observation was conducted by directly examining the company's condition and interviewing the owner, which revealed that Dinikoe Ceramics had not utilized social media effectively for promotion and still relied mainly on conventional methods that were insufficient to market the products. It was also found that promotional activities through social media videos were not yet optimal, leading to the agreement with the company owner to develop an additional promotional strategy in the form of advertising videos to be published on Instagram.

Planning

After the initial observation, the next step was the planning stage. At this stage, the researcher collected references from Instagram videos to understand good practices in video shooting and background music. Based on these references, a storyboard

was created containing information such as shop promotions, price offers, factory activities, and ordering details, presented in a short and clear format. Talent, dubbing, trending text, and background music were also included to attract the audience. The storyboard consisted of 11 scenes and 20 footages, and editing was planned to be done using the CapCut application.

Action

After completing the storyboard planning, the next step was video production at Dinikoe Ceramics, carried out both outside and inside the workshop at Jl. Telogo Suryo No. 48B, Lowokwaru, Malang. To make the video more engaging, talent was involved as the presenter. The production consisted of 9 scenes and 16 footages, packed into a 30-second format and recorded using a smartphone. Once filming was completed, the editing process began using the CapCut application. The steps included creating a new project, uploading footage, setting the aspect ratio to 9:16 for Instagram, choosing a thumbnail, muting default sounds, and adding background music. A bumper clip was also added at the beginning, while speed variations and keyframe zoom effects were applied to maintain viewer attention, especially during the ceramic-making process.

The editing process continued with the addition of a voice-over narration recorded via smartphone, which was enhanced using noise reduction for clarity. Smooth transitions and animations were applied between clips, while text overlays were inserted to provide product information in line with the company’s branding, using black-and-white fonts with a scribble outline style. Text animations were also included to emphasize key points and improve aesthetics. Finally, the video was rendered through the export feature in CapCut, producing the final output that was reviewed by both the company and the supervising lecturer before being published on Instagram.

Observation

After the video advertisement is finished, an observation is carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents to obtain an assessment of the video advertisement that has been shown. The assessments given by respondents will then be processed to review whether the video advertisement meets the criteria for advertising effectiveness and is suitable for use as a promotional medium. The distribution of questionnaires based on the effectiveness of the video advertisement design (EPIC Model) was distributed to 16 respondents, namely the owner of Dinoyo Ceramics Malang City, 1 employee, 2 marketing experts, 2 Design experts and 10 prospective buyers of Dinoyo Ceramics Malang City. The following are the results of the distribution of video advertisement questionnaires using the EPIC model, namely Empathy, Persuasion, Impact and Communication.

Table 1. Questionnaire distribution data

Question	Assessment Criteria				
	1	2	3	4	5
	STS	TS	N	S	SS
Empathy					
Like the design of Instagram posts Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City				3	13
The information contained in the design of the Instagram post Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City is easy to understand				8	8
The information on the Instagram post Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City is easy to remember				6	10
Persuasion					
The information on the design of the Instagram post Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City is trustworthy (according to reality)				9	7
The design of Instagram posts Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City can attract and convince buyers of the product				8	8
Impact					
The information on the design of Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City Instagram posts can provide buyers with knowledge about the company's history and product descriptions				5	11
Instagram posts Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City can provide knowledge to buyers about the benefits of the product				9	7
The design of Instagram posts Dinikoe Ceramics in Malang City can attract buying interest				9	7

Communication					
The design of Instagram posts of Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City makes it easier for buyers to understand the information conveyed				5	11

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Reflection

a. Empathy Dimension

Table 2. Empathy Dimension Questionnaire Assessment Results

Question	1	2	3	4	5	Average Item	Average Score Indicator
	STS	TS	N	S	SS		
<i>Empathy</i>							
Like the design of Instagram posts Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City				6	10	4,6	4,5
The information contained in the design of the Instagram post Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City is easy to understand				9	7	4,4	
The information on the Instagram post Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City is easy to remember				8	8	4,5	

Source: Processed Data (2025)

For more details, the calculation of the average score for each item and the average score of the Empathy dimension is as follows:

$$\text{Statement 1} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 6) + (5 \times 10)}{16} = 4,6$$

$$\text{Statement 2} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 9) + (5 \times 7)}{16} = 4,4$$

$$\text{Statement 3} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 8) + (5 \times 8)}{16} = 4,5$$

$$\text{Average Indicator} = \frac{(4,6 + 4,4 + 4,5)}{3} = 4,5$$

In table 2 based on the average score of the indicator, the measurement of effectiveness based on the EPIC Model Empathy dimension of promotional media in the form of Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City advertising video obtained a score of 4,5. So if positioned in the EPIC Model range it will be as follows:

Figure 2. EPIC Rate Scale Empathy Dimension Cycle I

Source: Processed data (2025)

b. Persuasion Dimension

Table 3. Persuasion Dimension Questionnaire Assessment Results

Question	1	2	3	4	5	Average Item	Average Score Indicator
	STS	TS	N	S	SS		
<i>Persuasion</i>							
The information on the design of the Instagram post Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City is trustworthy (according to reality)				9	7	4,4	4,4
The design of Instagram posts Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City can attract and convince buyers of the product				8	8	4,5	4,4

Source: Processed Data (2025)

For more details, the calculation of the average score for each item and the average score of the Empathy dimension is as follows:

$$\text{Statement 1} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 9) + (5 \times 7)}{16} = 4,4$$

$$\text{Statement 2} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 8) + (5 \times 8)}{16} = 4,5$$

$$\text{Average indicator} = \frac{(4,4 + 4,5)}{2} = 4,4$$

In table 3 based on the average score of the indicator, the measurement of effectiveness based on the EPIC Model Persuasion dimension of promotional media in the form of Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City advertising video obtained a score of 4,4. So if positioned in the EPIC Model range it will be as follows:

Figure 3. EPIC Rate Scale Persuasion Dimension Cycle I

Source: Processed data (2025)

c. Impact Dimension

Table 4. Impact Dimension Questionnaire Assessment Results

Question	1	2	3	4	5	Average Item	Average Score Indicator
	STS	TS	N	S	SS		
<i>Impact</i>							
The information on the design of Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City Instagram posts can provide buyers with knowledge about the company's history and product descriptions				5	11	4,6	4,4
Instagram posts Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City can provide knowledge to buyers about the benefits of the product				9	7	4,4	
The design of Instagram posts Dinikoe Ceramics in Malang City can attract buying interest				9	7	4,4	

Source: Processed Data (2025)

For more details, the calculation of the average score for each item and the average score of the Empathy dimension is as follows:

$$\text{Statement 1} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 5) + (5 \times 11)}{16} = 4,6$$

$$\text{Statement 2} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 9) + (5 \times 7)}{16} = 4,4$$

$$\text{Statement 3} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 9) + (5 \times 7)}{16} = 4,4$$

$$\text{Average Indicator} = \frac{(4,6 + 4,4 + 4,4)}{3} = 4,4$$

In table 4 based on the average score of the indicator, the measurement of effectiveness based on the EPIC Model Impact dimension of promotional media in the form of Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City advertising video obtained a score of 4,4. So if it is positioned in the EPIC Model range it will be as follows:

Figure 4. EPIC Rate Scale Impact Dimension Cycle I

Source: Processed data (2025)

d. Communication Dimension

Table 5. Communication Dimension Questionnaire Assessment Results

Question	1	2	3	4	5	Rataan peritem	Average Score Indicator
	STS	TS	N	S	SS		
Communication							
The design of Instagram posts of Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City makes it easier for buyers to understand the information conveyed				5	11	4,6	4,5
The design of the Instagram post Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City provides clear information				9	7	4,4	
The message conveyed in the Design Instagram posts of Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City is easy to understand				7	9	4,5	

Source: Processed Data (2025)

For more details, the calculation of the average score for each item and the average score of the Empathy dimension is as follows:

$$\text{Statement 1} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 5) + (5 \times 11)}{16} = 4,6$$

$$\text{Statement 2} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 9) + (5 \times 7)}{16} = 4,4$$

$$\text{Statement 3} = \frac{(1 \times 0) + (2 \times 0) + (3 \times 0) + (4 \times 7) + (5 \times 9)}{16} = 4,5$$

$$\text{Avarage Indicator} = \frac{(4,6 + 4,4 + 4,5)}{3} = 4,5$$

In table 5 based on the average score of the indicator, the measurement of effectiveness based on the EPIC Model Communication dimension of promotional media in the form of advertising videos for Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City obtained a score of 4,5. So if positioned in the EPIC Model range it will be as follows:

Figure 5. EPIC Rate Scale Communication Dimension

Source: Processed data (2025)

From the results of distributing questionnaires to videos, data was obtained related to the effectiveness of advertising video design. From the overall dimensions of EPIC (Emphaty. Persuasion, Impact, Communication), the results showed that the video had no respondents who gave the answer TS (Disagree) with a score of 2 or a score of 1 STS (Strongly Disagree) so that the advertising video was effective and ready to be published as a promotional media.

V. DISCUSSION

After obtaining data from the results of the questionnaire distribution and after processing the indicator data, a discussion was carried out regarding the calculation of the average score on all questionnaire indicators. The effectiveness of advertising video design with EPIC dimensions. The results of the calculation can be seen below :

$$\text{EPIC rate} = \frac{x \text{ Empati} + x \text{ Persuasi} + x \text{ Impact} + x \text{ Komunikasi}}{4}$$

$$\text{EPIC rate} = \frac{4,5 + 4,4 + 4,4 + 4,5}{4}$$

$$= 4,45$$

Judging from the tabulation for the EPIC dimension and supported by the Insights results obtained from Instagram, it can be concluded that the design of the advertising video as a promotional media at Dinikoe Ceramics Malang City is very effective for use as an information media. This is evidenced by the overall average score of the EPIC Rate, which is 4.45, where the score is included in the very effective category.

Figure 6. EPIC Rate Results

Source: Processed Data (2025)

VI. CONCLUSION

Dinikoe Ceramics Kota Malang is a home-based industry company engaged in the manufacture of ceramics. The use of social media as a promotional medium at Dinikoe Ceramics Kota Malang has been implemented, but it has not been maximized because it has not been managed properly. Therefore, an Instagram platform is needed, as the majority of Indonesians use it. With the creation of structured advertising videos, promotion at Dinikoe Ceramics Kota Malang will be more efficient.

This study employs the Action Research methodology. The research consists of a single cycle, beginning with the creation of a carefully designed advertising video, which is then uploaded to Dinikoe Ceramics Kota Malang's Instagram account. A questionnaire is subsequently distributed to 1 business owner, 1 factory employee, 2 design experts, 2 computer experts, and 10 potential customers. The results of the first cycle of the study were categorized as highly effective, with scores across all four dimensions: Empathy, Persuasion, Impact, and Communication. Based on the results of EPIC rate, the video advertisement design created by Dinikoe Ceramics in Malang City is deemed suitable for use as a promotional medium.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

A. For Companies

- Based on the research conducted, the following recommendations can be given to the owner of Dinikoe Ceramics Kota Malang:
1. It is hoped that Dinikoe Ceramics Kota Malang can increase its human resources to manage its Instagram social media account, which is useful for supporting promotional media and attracting consumer interest.
 2. It is hoped that the company can create and publish advertising videos on Instagram regularly so that they can be used effectively.
 3. It is hoped that the company can create attractive advertising videos on Instagram and provide clear and complete content for potential consumers.

B. For the Business Administration Department

- Based on the research that has been conducted, the following recommendations are made for the department:
1. It is hoped that the department can facilitate and expand the learning of advertising video design. With more editing applications being studied in depth by students, this will greatly help and benefit students in honing their skills.
 2. It is hoped that the advertising videos that have been created can be developed and optimized by subsequent researchers, so that the promotional media provided to the public does not stop at this research alone.

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